

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE NEED FOR INNOVATION IN THE SPHERE OF HOUSING AND COMMUNAL SERVICES IN UKRAINE

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ABSTRACT

The continuous growth of prices for energy resources, determined by their growing scarcity, makes inevitable the transition of housing and communal services to innovative and resource-energy-saving technologies. The unsatisfactory condition of the housing stock, the high level of wear of engineering networks and equipment, inefficient management structure determine the need for modernization of the industry based on innovative technologies.

Objective.

Development of methodological approaches to the implementation of innovations in the sphere of reforming housing and communal services in Ukraine.

Results.

Determined indicators to assess the impact of the results of innovations on the quality of services in the system of housing and communal services. The stated theoretical generalizations and practical information contribute to the formation of a system-structural model for the introduction of innovations in the sphere of housing and communal services in Ukraine.

Conclusions.

Based on the carried-out research it is defined, that actions on formation of innovative strategy should be focused on well formulated strategic purposes of reforming housing and communal services. The received results can serve as a basis for the further introduction of innovations in the context of reformation of the sphere of housing and communal services.

Keywords: Housing and communal services; innovations; implementation; technology, housing and communal services, communal infrastructure, management of innovation, mutually beneficial relations.

1.1. Introduction

Analysis of the activity of Ukrainian enterprises revealed the potential of energy saving, accounting for a quarter of the annual consumption of energy resources in the country. However, the used outdated technologies and lack of motivation to save resources do not allow to realize this potential. The poorly developed system of economic relations between the entities of the housing and communal sector today does not allow for the effective use and introduction of innovative technologies and energy-saving principles. Based on methodological and empirical aspects of system factors, based on domestic experience, and applied approaches of already tested results, the author's conceptual vision of the prospects for further research into the problem of reforming the housing and communal services through the introduction of innovation is presented.

1.2. Materials and methods

Application of methodical approach to the measurement of innovation potential of housing and communal services using the analytical method.

1.3. Results

The housing and communal economy (HCS) of Ukraine is a multi-branch economic complex, which includes more than 25 sub-branches and more than 70 types of economic activity. The housing and utilities sector takes 26% of the national economy's fixed assets, which is just behind the transport sector (29.5%) and industry (27.4%).

The wear and tear of utility infrastructure is over 60%, about 25% of fixed assets have fully served their useful life. Wear and tear of engineering equipment have reached 73%, engineering networks - 65%. The reliability of heat supply systems is 2.5 times lower than in European countries. Every year less than 1% of networks are overhauled instead of the minimum allowable 3%. The number of technological violations and accidents in the work of communal facilities has increased fivefold over the past 10 years. Every year there are on average 70 accidents per 100 km of water supply networks and 200 accidents per 100 km of heat supply networks. Scheduled repair of engineering networks and equipment of water supply and municipal

energy systems almost completely gave way to emergency recovery works, the cost of which is 3 times higher than the cost of scheduled and major repairs of similar facilities. The financial condition of housing and utility organizations continues to deteriorate, more than 60% of organizations are unprofitable, so the housing and utilities sector is one of the underdeveloped and underinvested areas of entrepreneurship.

That is why the reform of housing and communal services has become one of the priority issues of state socio-economic policy, which should combine the adoption and implementation of economically justified administrative, personnel, technical, technological, institutional, financial, social, political, and other decisions, and must make the population participants of the reform processes of housing and communal services, as one of the vital areas of the national economy [1].

Several contradictions have accumulated that require urgent solutions: market development in the housing and utilities sector and outdated regulatory framework, high stock intensity and low productivity in the housing and utility sector, stagnation in the structural development of the housing and utility sector, and accelerated growth of the entrepreneurial environment in the economy in general, rising tariffs on housing and utilities and deteriorating financial status of enterprises, lack of public participation in creating new organizational-legal forms of homeowners associations and the need for active involvement in the housing and utilities sector [2].

Thus, the need to resolve these contradictions makes it imperative to bring the housing and utilities sector into a form that would be adequate to the dynamics of the modern business environment and consider the interests of homeowners, suppliers, service providers, and the state.

The system of housing and communal services (HCS) is the result of interaction between the consumer and the service provider, as well as the activity of the provider, which is aimed at maximizing the satisfaction of the desires, needs, and preferences of the consumer.

In this regard, the formation of a structural model of innovation management in the system of housing and communal services based on considering the totality of the requirements of all participants in the process of implementation of housing and communal activities is an important task. In addition, the model based on the principles of the quality management system and innovation management, in modern conditions of development of the domestic economy is one of the factors in ensuring the efficiency and competitiveness of the utility enterprise.

The quality management system of housing and communal services enterprises can be considered as a complex of administrative, technological, social, and legal processes that ensure the organization's ability to provide guaranteed services that meet the requirements of the consumer in accordance with current legislation and state regulatory documents governing the provision of housing and communal services (HCS).

The innovation management system of housing and communal services enterprise can be considered as

a complex of innovative developments, modern technologies, ideas to optimize the management process of the communal enterprise.

The efficiency of the enterprise as one of the economic entities in the economic system depends on the relationship with all parties involved in one way or another in the provision or consumption of housing and utility services, as well as services that regulate in the field of housing and utilities, among them can be distinguished:

- homeowners; tenants of housing; tenants of premises;
- creditors;
- representatives of insurance companies;
- suppliers of communal resources;
- employees of service organizations;
- State Housing Inspectorate;
- municipal inspection.

In market conditions, a partner (contractor) is chosen depending on the expectations of quality, price, and timing of obligations. Ensuring a stable level of quality of service (supplied products) is provided by the implementation of quality management system [3].

The approach to improving the efficiency of management of innovative activities of housing and communal services based on the implementation of innovative measures includes two important processes: the process of development and implementation of the principles of management of innovative activities of housing and communal services and the process of standardization and certification of the services provided.

Organization of the process of development and implementation of the principles of management of innovative activity in the system of housing and communal services requires addressing two types of factors:

housing and communal services provided within the complex of housing and communal services, as well as any other services, should be subject to the principles of service quality management system;

innovative development of housing and communal services, must comply with the principles of innovation management.

In this regard, it is advisable to define a set of principles of innovation management in the system of housing and communal services, based on the system of quality management and innovation management:

- Principle of state stimulation.
- The principle of consumer interests.
- The principle of multifaceted results.
- The principle of substitution.
- The principle of effective control.
- The principle of mass innovation.
- Correct Assessment Principle.
- Principle of a prompt response.
- Principle of loss minimization.
- The principle of payback in perspective.
- The principle of environmental safety.

The process of implementation of principles of management of innovative activity in housing and communal services system is based on development and description of certain rules and algorithms of work of the

managing company and accountable persons in conditions of innovations implementation. This process implies that the operations performed in the provision of services based on the introduction of innovations should be placed under the control of responsible persons and that orders, decisions, and orders, will be brought to a specific performer, and executed at the required level.

The presented principles and factors of innovative development must be considered in the development of an innovative approach to improving the effectiveness of the management of the utility enterprise. In addition, it is necessary to consider the principles of implementation of innovative housing and communal services, which allow ensuring the proper quality through compliance with a certain set of established requirements.

The first group of requirements, public services based on the introduction of innovations must strictly meet the system of quality standards, standards, technical and sanitary requirements, conditions of the concluded contract.

The second group of requirements, public services based on the introduction of innovations must meet the needs and expectations of the consumer, the requirements dictated by the charter of the enterprise, rules, codes, norms for the protection of the environment, and the welfare of the housing stock. And it is the consumer (homeowner or initiative group) who must evaluate the impact of innovations on the quality-of-service provider.

To make a full-fledged comprehensive assessment, it is necessary to develop a methodical approach and a system of indicators to assess the impact of the results of innovation on the quality of services in the housing and communal services system. This system should be based on the following groups of indicators (Table 1). Calculation of these indicators makes it possible to determine the state in which the company is and assess the quality of services provided.

The third group of requirements, public service must be built based on an economically justified tariff that can satisfy all parties to the utility relationship and be beneficial to them.

Table 1.

Indicators for assessing the impact of innovation results on the quality of services in the housing and communal services system

Group of indicators	Indicator
Environmental Performance Indicators.	Dynamics of changes in water quality. The level of realization of solid domestic waste. Assessment of changes in the level of contamination of adjacent areas.
Technical and operational indicators.	Assessment of changes in the speed of processing the application, and the quality of its execution. Assessment of the condition of the residential facility. Assessment of the condition of the engineering equipment. Degree of uninterrupted supply of housing and communal services and their compliance with the normative values.
Indicators of resource conservation.	Reducing electricity consumption. Reduction of gas consumption. Decrease in water consumption. Grid water losses. Grid power losses. Grid gas losses.
Organizational and economic indicators.	The level of transparency of tariff policy. The level of transparency of economic relations. Dynamics of the solvency of users of Utility and housing services. Degree of residents' confidence in the managing company. The level of complaints about the provision of services.

Further reform of housing and communal services becomes impossible without the application of new forms and methods of management of the housing stock of Ukrainian cities for this purpose it is necessary to create mechanisms to stimulate the creation of associations of owners of apartment buildings (condominiums) and other organizations that unite them:

- to legally oblige the authorities to carry out major repairs of residential premises when they are transferred to condominiums;
- to develop and adopt simple mechanisms of crediting owners of apartment buildings to pay for capital repairs of the property in shared ownership;

- cancel the registration procedure for condominiums as non-profit organizations, due to the fact that it complicates the registration procedure, but does not provide tax benefits;

- oblige authorities to provide financial assistance to housing and communal enterprises (if necessary) only after consultation with condominiums.

Successful reform of the housing and utilities sector requires the creation of a unified regulatory and legal framework based on interconnected and well-thought-out legislative initiatives and regulatory legal acts. Information support is one of the priorities of the reform of the housing and utilities sector. As a result of

analysis of the state of information support of the management system of housing and communal services in the cities of Ukraine revealed several significant problems:

- the constant need for residents to address each of the participants in the sphere of housing and communal services separately, entails unreasonable psycho-physical and time costs;
- the lack of a unified approach to management, taking into account the interaction of all managed processes occurring with the subject under management;
- absence of a unified and accessible information database on the subjects and objects of the housing and communal services;
- unreasonable and multiple duplications of data in different information systems.

To implement the main directions of reforming the housing and utilities sector, it is necessary to solve the tasks determining the content and successful functioning of the information support of the housing and utilities sector management system and the city economy automation system inseparably connected with it.

A sound innovation policy presupposes both introductions of innovations at the enterprises of the sector and the creation of mechanisms for their adaptation and development in the existing structure of production. Innovations are the main mechanism that provides effective development of production and maintenance of economic potential [4].

In this connection, it is advisable to create sectoral regional innovation centers for reforming the housing and utilities sector, whose main activities may include the following:

- testing and testing of innovative developments in conditions similar to the operating conditions of these systems in the housing and utilities sector and implementation of these developments in practical activities;
- organization and conduct of research to assess the status and prospects of development of the quality management system in the housing and communal services sector in large cities
- certification of the quality of services provided by housing and communal economy enterprises;
- training and skills upgrading of the staff of the housing and communal economy enterprises.

The creation of such Centers on their basis of educational, scientific, and administrative resources will make it possible to create a system of quality management in the sphere of housing and communal services and thus start the implementation of the housing and communal services reform. In general, we can state that the following changes are needed in the housing and utilities sector:

- radical renewal of obsolete equipment for modern and more efficient ones;

- competent personnel selection and retraining of the existing staff;
- increase of investors' interest in the sphere of housing and communal services and support of the state for implementation of innovative management systems.

Implementation of these measures will make it possible to apply technological developments of Ukrainian engineers, replace worn-out and obsolete equipment and network communications with long-term qualitative developments, which will lead to significant savings of taxpayers' financial resources, improve the quality of life of the population, especially those living in the worn-out housing stock.

The structural model of innovation management in the housing and communal services system implies control over technical, organizational, economic, environmental, and human factors. Controls are measures of measurement, examination, or evaluation of one or more characteristics of a product or service and comparison of the results with the established requirements to determine their compliance with these requirements. [5].

Such control with the purpose of preventing, reducing, eliminating failures and excessive interruptions in the provision of public services should be the basis of the control system, which includes the following methods:

- instrumental control (measuring the condition of utilities with various testers, devices; measuring consumption volumes with meters; checking water quality with appropriate tools; humidity and temperature in rooms with thermometers);
- audit control (inspection and analysis of documents, acceptance reports of installation and commissioning works, maintenance logs, certificates of materials used);
- visual inspection (examination of the engineering networks, the building, the adjacent structures, the quality of the installation work);
- sociological control (questioning, interviewing a focus group consisting of consumers of utilities).

In addition, a significant part of control in the housing and utilities sector is impossible without consumer participation. Therefore, the structure of consumer control in the quality of services provided can be presented in the form of three elements, guaranteeing the independence and completeness of control: (Figure 1) [6].

- regional control, based on the principle of one-time inspections - planned or upon requests of citizens and enterprises;
- control at the level of a municipality, based on the systematic work on control and prevention of violations;
- control of owners (society of consumers, public chamber of the city).

Fig. 1. Structural model of innovation management in the system of housing and communal services.

The main advantages of the proposed structural model of innovative activity management in the housing and communal services system are:

- formation of more effective management by taking into account the principles of innovative development of housing and communal services and taking into account a variety of factors affecting this process;
- the management process is built according to the requirements of the system of existing standards for the quality of housing and communal services;
- investment of innovative measures aimed at reducing costs for the provision and consumption of public services that have been carried out under the housing and communal services modernization program;
- improvement and informatization of the accounting system for financial and other costs and making this information freely available to all participants in housing and communal relations.

As shown by the analysis, the investment policy of housing and communal services in the subjects of Ukraine is ineffective. To improve the efficiency of housing and communal services we propose a program aimed at increasing investment activity in the housing and communal services.

In modern conditions, Ukraine cannot allow blind copying and application in the Ukrainian practice of national economy management theories and concepts that are effective in Western Europe and the United States. Undoubtedly, it is necessary to use the achievements of advanced world economic thought, but with the obligatory account of Ukrainian national characteristics, mentality, customs, and way of life. That was developed by scientists-economists and successfully implemented in other countries, cannot and should not be applied in modern conditions of Ukraine without considering Ukrainian features, because the way of life of peoples of many foreign countries and Ukrainians, including in the sphere of housing, simply not comparable.

1.4. Discussion

Given the analysis of the specific functioning of the system of housing and communal services in Ukraine requires the development of a special strategy to overcome the crisis of housing and communal services and the transition to the solution of the accumulated socio-economic problems in the framework of the development of innovative economy in Ukraine. This is possible through the implementation of effective innovation and investment policy.

The reform of the housing and utilities sector is complex, large-scale, and affects all spheres of activity: investment, credit, economic-financial, organizational-legal, social-political, environmental, technical, and others. The reform of the housing and utilities sector must improve the performance of its sectors and their reliability for consumers. As a practical result of the previously conducted research, the author proposes a program for reforming the housing and utilities sector at the present stage. This program includes several necessary measures in some areas of the housing and utilities sector.

1.4.1. Necessary measures in investment activity:

1.4.1.1. To solve the problem of attracting investments in the housing and utilities sector of Ukraine, an effective investment policy, which is a set of approaches and decisions determining the volume, structure, and directions of the use of investments, is necessary. Until recently, the policy in the field of investments was the prerogative of the state, making decisions on "horizontal" and "vertical" redistribution of investments. Investment crises proved the inefficiency of such a system, and the regulation of investment activity is gradually shifting to the level where the current development tasks and possible methods of stimulation are better visible. In general, the investment policy of the housing and utilities sector should be focused on:

- to create a favorable investment climate;
- determination of the volumes and structure of investments which are reasonable for each period;

- for the choice of priorities;
- to increase the efficiency of investments. To effectively solve the problems of formation and implementation of the investment policy of Ukraine should first:

a) determine the principles of formation and implementation of the investment policy of housing and communal services, the peculiarities of the development of investment activity of housing and communal services, which are formed under the influence of factors of both endogenous and exogenous nature, and methods of management of investment activity of housing and communal services: administrative and administrative, economic, social and psychological, innovative, etc.;

b) to form the functions of the management of investment activity of housing and communal services: planning, organization, motivation, coordination, and control, as well as effective interrelations in the sphere of housing and communal services between the subjects and objects at all levels of management. In addition, it is necessary to clearly understand the essence of investment relations of participants in the sphere of housing and communal services in the context of interaction and implementation of their investment needs and interests.

The tasks of the mechanism of formation and implementation of the investment policy of housing and communal services are, firstly, the formation of strategy and tactics of management of investment activity of housing and communal services and, secondly, the introduction of new forms and methods of management, improvement of the organization of management of investment activity of housing and communal services, development of competitive relations.

The effective investment policy will allow ensuring:

- implementation of long-term investment objectives of socio-economic development of the housing and utilities sector of Ukraine;
- assessment of investment opportunities of the housing and utilities sector, as well as the maximum use of internal investment potential and the ability to actively maneuver investment resources;
- possibility of fast implementation of new perspective investment decisions, which appear in the process of dynamic changes of the external environment factors;
- determination of investment activity to specify managerial decisions of investment nature.

1.4.1.2. The negative trend of an increasing discrepancy between the growth rate of prices for housing and communal services and their quality, as well as the level of income of the population requires the implementation of such state policy (investment, tariff, and pricing), which would consider the interests of specific producers and consumers of housing and communal services, as well as the state and society in this area.

1.4.1.3. As shown by the results of the study, first, it is necessary to eliminate the following main problems that negatively affect the formation and implementation of the investment policy of housing and communal services:

- administrative barriers, affecting issues of regulatory and legal regulation, the formation of an effective mechanism of interaction between state authorities at the state level and local levels between themselves, business, the population, as well as economic incentives and responsibility for the inefficient use of the services provided;

- absence of mechanisms and tools for investment. Today we need large investments from various economic entities, money at low-interest rates, minimization of investment risks;

- inefficient management, contributing to the formation of the unattractiveness of the sphere of housing and communal services for investment [7]. Search for investment resources, optimization of investment structure, effective investment of investment funds in areas that ensure socio-economic growth of the industry - these are the challenges facing managers, whose work should use modern management tools;

- information disclosure. Currently, there is no information for investors about the objects of possible investment in the public domain. Managers of most utilities have no information related to the issues of organizing investment, about possible mechanisms of co-investment, and have no experience in organizing the investment process.

1.4.1.4. Currently, there is a need to establish realistic rates of development of the investment sphere, to determine planned indicators of investment, to form their structure, the list of target programs, and investment projects to be practically implemented in a particular planning period based on multivariate forecast calculations. Investment forecasting is a complex, multi-stage process of studying the probabilistic aspects of capital investment in one or another sphere of the economy in the future [8].

1.4.2. Necessary measures to improve legislation:

1.4.2.1. Currently, regulation of prices and tariffs for certain housing and communal services is performed by executive authorities, but Ukrainian legislation stipulates that local self-government bodies independently manage the municipal property and have the right to independently set tariffs (prices) for services provided by municipal enterprises.

Now local governments do not have sufficient financial independence, and revenues of local budgets do not correspond to the volume of spending powers of local governments. In this connection, the latter are not always interested in effective management of investment activities, creation of favorable conditions for development and modernization in the sphere of housing and utilities, and do not have the ability to implement an effective long-term policy in this area.

Only the independence of municipalities can serve as a basis for the real responsibility of local governments for the results of activities in the sphere of housing and communal services. That is why it is necessary to prepare a draft law stipulating the procedure of state regulation of tariffs and prices for housing and communal services with a clear indication of those housing and communal services, in respect of which the state regu-

lation is carried out. In addition, it is necessary to delineate the powers of state and local authorities in this sphere.

1.4.2.2. Regulatory and legal support of the housing and communal sector development shall be carried out at the state, regional and municipal levels.

1.4.2.3. Reform of the housing and communal sector should be aimed at forming a budgetary system that would allow an optimal distribution of investment resources between the levels of the budgetary system and a balance of budgets at different levels. That is why budgetary and tax legislation should provide for:

- clear assignment of revenue sources and spending powers to the budgets of different levels;
- creation of specific mechanisms for investment support to local budgets;
- reducing the number of financial obligations imposed by legislation on local budgets without the provision of funding sources.

1.4.2.4. The most important promising sources of investment in projects to modernize and develop the housing and communal complex should be private investment. The need to attract non-state investment to eliminate the crisis in the housing and utilities sector is undoubted. In this connection, it is necessary to prepare a draft law envisaging measures aimed at attracting investments from various sources to the housing and utilities sector and establish a most favorable investment climate there. For this purpose, the draft law should define the basis, forms, and procedure for encouraging investment activities, as well as the conditions and principles of state support of this sphere.

1.4.2.5. It is necessary to introduce amendments into the Housing Code of Ukraine concerning:

- provision of discounts by the supplier of housing and communal services in case of regular advance payments for these services;
- toughening responsibility for dishonest payers for housing and communal services;
- introduction of fines for managing companies or resource supplying organizations for the low-quality provision of housing and communal services and (or) in cases of presenting wrong bills for these services in favor of consumers of housing and communal services.

1.4.3. Necessary measures in the issues of interaction with innovative and other spheres of the economy of Ukraine:

1.4.3.1. It is necessary to introduce innovative technologies in the activities of housing and communal enterprises, providing waste-free disposal of domestic and industrial waste, primarily in the territories of Ukraine with a special regime of nature management, and (or) using special management regimes, including more advanced treatment facilities, the introduction of water recycling systems, reconstruction and modernization of industrial production, development, and implementation of environmentally safe technologies.

1.4.3.2. The funds released by the reduction of state subsidies in housing and communal services due to the transition to 100% payment for housing and communal services by the population of Ukraine should be directed to the creation of new or reconstruction of ex-

isting industrial areas, including engineering and communication infrastructure (boiler houses, water intake, purification stations, etc.) of the industrial territory, on which technoparks, business incubators will be created to accommodate small innovative enterprises specializing primarily in the development of the industrial sector.

There is an urgent need for technoparks to provide system innovations in the field of technological and organizational modernization of enterprises in the housing and utility sector, energy-saving and energy efficiency in the housing and utilities sector, etc. "Cultivation" in business incubators of small companies will promote the introduction of new technologies, the use of innovations to solve the problems of housing and communal services, medicine, ecology, and other areas within the area of responsibility of public administration of housing and communal services, increasing the innovative activity of business in Ukraine as a whole [9].

1.4.3.3. It is necessary to create in Ukraine information systems that are information and technological environment of storage, processing, analysis, and dissemination of information in the field of innovations and investments in the housing and utilities sector in the interests of state bodies, economic entities, and citizens, first to implement effective innovation and investment policy in the housing and utilities sector.

The creation of such an information system requires, first, uniting all existing data storage in the housing and utilities sector into "one window" that will exclude duplication of information flows and create a basis for the further transition to a qualitatively new level of providing public authorities and management activities. This is especially important in view of the key, connecting role of information in the implementation of innovation and investment cycles, which consist of separate functionally isolated stages: fundamental and applied research, experimental development, preparation for pilot production, serial production, sales. All this will ensure the synergistic effect of interrelated and highly effective joint implementation of innovation and investment cycles. It is suggested to place information about the situation in innovative and investment spheres of this sector on websites of ministries and departments supervising the housing and utilities sector.

1.4.3.4. Overcoming the crisis in the housing and utilities sector should be linked to a comprehensive solution of socially important problems: raising the population's incomes; taking measures to ensure timely payment of wages, and strengthening control over the observance of people's labor rights.

1.4.3.5. There is a need to set up a system to register the actual volumes of services consumed by the population, define a minimal set of services, without which payment for communal services can't be collected.

1.4.3.6. Reform of the housing and utility sector should be carried out in the interests of the poor through an effective system of targeted state assistance to them to pay for housing and utility services.

1.4.4. Ways to achieve the main objectives in the sphere of reforming the housing and utilities sector.

The main objectives in the sphere of the housing and utility sector are the provision of the population with living conditions that meet quality standards; reduction of costs of service producers and, accordingly, tariffs while maintaining quality standards of services provided; mitigation of the process of reforming the housing and utilities payment system for the population while transitioning to a break-even operation; transition to self-sufficiency in the industry. To achieve these goals, it is necessary to use the following methods:

- improvement of the management, operation, and control system;
- transition to self-financing of sectoral organizations by reducing, and in the future end, the budgetary allocations for grants, and eliminating cross-subsidies;
- raising housing and communal services rates for the population to an economically sound level based on a competitive selection process for the organizations that provide these services.
- In addition, to achieve the goals, set, it is necessary to solve the following key tasks:
 - to create and improve economic and organizational mechanisms to reduce the cost of housing and communal services while maintaining and improving their quality and sustainability of the industry;
 - improve the tariff policy for housing and communal services in order to achieve a balance between the financial needs of service providers and the solvency of consumers [10];
 - reduce budgetary subsidies to the industry and use the released budgetary resources for social purposes.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the goal of the proposed program of housing and communal services reform at the present stage is to improve the reliability and sustainability of the sector enterprises and improve the quality of housing and communal services with a simultaneous relative reduction of costs for their provision, which is the optimal solution to the problem.

1.5. Conclusions

Innovations allow the introduction of new equipment, machines, and mechanisms, considering the current technical requirements, standards, and regulations. Of course, the effective operation of all systems requires competent and qualified specialists who have vast experience in this area of activity. Only in this case, it is possible to implement innovations without difficulties, as well as to carry out their maintenance, which is necessary for their full operation.

The role of information technology in the implementation of socio-economic development in the whole country has increased. The use of innovations will

change the principles of interaction of government agencies with organizations and citizens and increase the efficiency of interaction and information transfer. Without the creation of comprehensive software, it is impossible to organize the rational management of government agencies at all levels. Information technology is becoming an important tool for solving problems in the transition of housing and communal services of Ukraine on the path of innovation. The introduction of innovative technologies in the organization of housing and communal complex will provide an opportunity to form operational and reliable information about the state of housing and communal services. Also make it possible to make effective management decisions, for example, in regulating the cost of housing and communal services. It is necessary to help in the implementation of innovative technologies in the activities of economic entities of the sphere of housing and communal services.

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